

Supplementary Information

Soft X-ray Emission Spectroscopy on Phosphorus Containing Compounds for Energy Conversion and Storage

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1. Further experimental details for the P $L_{2,3}$ -edge resonant inelastic X-ray scattering (RIXS), P $L_{2,3}$ X-ray emission spectroscopy (XES), P L_3 XES, and P $L_{2,3}$ X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) measurements

This section contains details on the P $L_{2,3}$ -edge resonant inelastic X-ray scattering (RIXS), P $L_{2,3}$ XES, and P L_3 XES measurements, such as the energy steps for the RIXS/XES measurements, as well as energy resolution of the XES experiments.

Further experimental information on P $L_{2,3}$ XAS (e.g., details on PFY-XAS integration, energy resolution, etc) is provided in previous work ¹.

1.1. Experimental details for P $L_{2,3}$ -edge RIXS

P $L_{2,3}$ -edge RIXS experiments were conducted in the iRIXS end-station ² at BL 8.0.1 of the Advanced Light Source (ALS) ³, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL), USA. RIXS data were recorded using a high-throughput (HT) spectrometer installed at the beamline ². Measurements were conducted with the low-energy grating of the spherical grating monochromator (SGM) with an entrance and exit slit size of 50 μm for all experiments.

Details of energy steps and the integration time for the RIXS measurements of each P-containing compound are provided in **Table S1**.

Table S1. Energy steps and integration time for RIXS of each P-containing compound.

Samples	Energy range (eV); energy steps (eV)	XES integration time for each excitation energy (seconds)
GaP ⁽³⁻⁾ , InP ⁽³⁻⁾	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 125.0 – 128.0 ; 0.5• 128.2 – 130.0 ; 0.2• 130.1 –132.5 ; 0.1• 132.7 –137.0 ; 0.2• 137.5 –152.0 ; 0.5	45
Red-P ⁽⁰⁾	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 125.0 – 130.0 ; 0.3• 130.1 – 134.0 ; 0.1• 134.2 –137.0 ; 0.1• 132.7 –137.0 ; 0.2• 137.5 –152.0 ; 0.5	30
H ₃ P ⁽³⁺⁾ O ₃	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 130.0 – 135.0 ; 0.5• 135.2 – 136.0 ; 0.2• 136.1 – 142.0 ; 0.1	60

Samples	Energy range (eV); energy steps (eV)	XES integration time for each excitation energy (seconds)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 142.2 – 151.0 ; 0.2 • 151.5 – 155.0 ; 0.5 	
Na₂H₂P₂⁽⁴⁺⁾O₆	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 130.0 – 134.0 ; 0.5 • 134.2 – 137.0 ; 0.2 • 137.1 – 144.0 ; 0.1 • 144.2 – 151.0 ; 0.2 • 151.5 – 156.0 ; 0.5 	60
H₃P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, KH₂P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, Na₂HP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 130.0 – 135.0 ; 0.5 • 135.2 – 136.0 ; 0.2 • 136.1 – 142.0 ; 0.1 • 142.2 – 151.0 ; 0.2 • 151.5 – 155.0 ; 0.5 	60
InP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 130.0 – 134.0 ; 0.5 • 134.2 – 137.0 ; 0.2 • 137.1 – 144.0 ; 0.1 • 144.2 – 151.0 ; 0.2 • 151.5 – 156.0 ; 0.5 	60

The excitation energy steps used for the RIXS measurements were varied in different regions relative to the absorption onset, and for display, the RIXS maps were linearly interpolated onto a uniform excitation energy axis with a step size corresponding to the smallest step used in the measurements; a larger step was used to probe the onset and post-edge regions where no additional information was expected to be gained from smaller steps. The emission energy was calibrated using the elastic peak in the RIXS maps, see the bright diagonal features at the bottom right in each panel in **Figure S1**, considering that its energy is the same as the excitation energy. Interpolation and energy calibration were conducted with an IGOR Pro script for analysis of RIXS dataset acquired at the iRIXS end-station. To account for possible variations in the intensity of the incoming beam that could affect the intensity of the recorded RIXS spectra, the RIXS spectra were normalized to the intensity of the incoming photons measured with a Au-mesh located upstream of the measurement chamber. Careful observation of the spectral shape of the collected data during (subsequent) measurements or in different beamtime campaigns did not provide any obvious indications for beam damage on the 10-seconds and a few minutes timescale.

1.2. Experimental details for P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES

Following RIXS measurements, P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES were recorded with the same experimental setup and configuration as the P $L_{2,3}$ -edge RIXS experiments detailed in the previous section. In particular, all P $L_{2,3}$ XES data were recorded with the excitation energy of 158 eV, which is at least 20 eV above the P L_3 absorption-edge of the P-containing compounds. The P L_3 XES measurements on each compound were performed with the excitation energies listed in **Table S2**. These energies were chosen to be slightly higher (0.1 to 0.6 eV) than the P L_3 -edge of the sample, to specifically excite the P L_3 -edge transition (but not the P L_2 -edge), given that the doublet separation of P-containing compounds ranging from 0.7 - 1.0 eV. The P L_3 absorption-edge was determined through the inflection point of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS, see Ref. ¹. **Figure S1** illustrates the RIXS maps and the respective excitation energy used for the P L_3 measurements of each P-containing compound. For both P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES, the spectra were collected with an integration time of 15 minutes (15 CCD images were recorded, each was recorded for 60 seconds).

Table S2. Excitation energy used in the P L_3 XES measurements of P-containing compounds.

Samples	L_3-edge Excitation energy (eV)
GaP⁽³⁻⁾	131.29
InP⁽³⁻⁾	131.02
Red-P⁽⁰⁾	131.62
H₃P⁽³⁺⁾O₃	137.30
Na₂H₂P₂⁽⁴⁺⁾O₆	137.44
H₃P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	137.99
KH₂P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	137.50
Na₂HP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	137.40
InP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄	138.39

Figure S1. P $L_{2,3}$ -edge RIXS maps, P $L_{2,3}$ (PFY) XAS, and the respective excitation energy for the P L_3 XES experiments (indicated by a dashed line) of: (A) GaP $^{3-}$, (B) InP $^{3-}$, (C) red-P $^{(0)}$, (D) H $_3$ P $^{3+}$ O $_3$, (E) Na $_2$ H $_2$ P $_2^{(4+)}$ O $_6$, (F) H $_3$ P $^{(5+)}$ O $_4$, (G) KH $_2$ P $^{(5+)}$ O $_4$, (H) Na $_2$ HP $^{(5+)}$ O $_4$, and (I) InP $^{(5+)}$ O $_4$. Please note that the oscillation-like signal observed in the baseline of some compounds (e.g., panels A and H) likely originates from baseline noise rather than any physical features of the sample, presumably due to the low fluorescence yield of the P $L_{2,3}$ transitions.

1.3. Estimation of the energy resolution for the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES data

The XES experimental energy resolutions were approximated by the square root summation of: (i) the resolution of the exciting photon from the beamline, (ii) the natural width of the probed transition, and (iii) the resolution of the high throughput spectrometer used to record the XES, i.e., with Eq. (S1).

$$\sigma_{\text{XES exp. res.}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{BL. exc. photon.}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{nat. width}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{spectrometer}}^2}. \quad (\text{S1})$$

In our measurement setup, which utilizes the low-energy monochromator grating with an entrance and exit slit size of 50 μm to monochromatize incoming X-rays, the monochromator has a resolution of approximately 0.13 eV. The natural width of the P $L_{2,3}$ -edge transition is 0.03 eV⁴. Considering that 3.5 pixels of the high-throughput spectrometer CCD are needed to resolve the energy², the resolution of the spectrometer is defined as $3.5 \times$ the emission energy steps. Since the emission energy steps are different for lower and higher photon energy, the resolution of the spectrometer is approximated at an emission energy of about 132 eV, which is the highest XES photon energy discussed in the main text. At higher photon energies, the emission energy steps are larger, leading to increased uncertainty in spectrometer measurements. Therefore, estimation provides the maximum energy resolution for the XES. Around 132 eV, the emission energy step is 0.02 eV, which translates to a spectrometer resolution of 0.08 eV. Using these values and Eq. (S1), the XES energy resolution is estimated to be 0.16 eV.

2. Further details on P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES data analysis

This section contains further details on the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES data analysis, including: (i) subtraction of the cosmic rays from the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra; (ii) subtraction of the O K -edge 4th order X-ray emission from both the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra; (iii) estimation of electronic band gap from P L_3 XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS data; and (iv) Alignment of P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS data with *ab initio* calculated pDOS.

2.1. Subtraction of cosmic rays from the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra of P-containing compounds

Since cosmic rays are recorded during the acquisition of the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra, their presence is detected and subtracted from the XES data. If a data point exhibits a significantly higher intensity compared to its neighboring points, it is likely an outlier caused by a cosmic ray impact. Data points exceeding the range $Q_3 \pm 1.5 IQR$, where Q_3 is the third quartile and IQR the interquartile range, are considered outliers in a normal distribution. To assess the potential influence of cosmic rays on recorded data points, the following procedure is employed:

- (1) First, Q_3 and IQR are assessed every 20 data points of the XES spectrum (note that each XES spectrum has an emission energy step comprised between 0.017 eV and 0.022 eV). The IQR is defined as $IQR = Q_3 - Q_1$, in which Q_1 is the first quartile in the assessed XES range.
- (2) Within the assessed XES range, the threshold intensity value for outliers is determined as $I_{\text{outlier}} > Q_3 \pm 2 IQR$. A value of $2 IQR$ was used instead of $1.5 IQR$, to make sure that the XES spectra were not oversubtracted.
- (3) For each data point in the emission energy, the intensity of that data point I_i is compared to I_{outlier} .
- (4) If $I_i > I_{\text{outlier}}$, then the data point is considered to contain cosmic ray contributions and is thus excluded from the XES spectra.

Figures S2 illustrates the P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectra of all considered P-containing compounds before and after the subtraction procedure of cosmic ray contributions. No significant contribution of cosmic rays were recorded in the P L_3 XES spectra.

Figure S2. P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectra **(A)** before cosmic ray subtraction and **(B)** after cosmic rays subtraction. The sharp increase in the intensity of $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ XES spectra at 121 eV in panel (A) illustrates the recorded cosmic rays.

2.2. Subtraction of Oxygen *K*-edge 4th order emission from the P *L*_{2,3} XES and P *L*₃ XES spectra of P-containing compounds

For the oxygen-containing phosphorus compounds, H₃P⁽³⁺⁾O₃, Na₂H₂P₂⁽⁴⁺⁾O₆, H₃P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, KH₂P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, Na₂HP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, and InP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, a 4th order O *K*-edge emission (excited by higher harmonics of the undulator and hereafter referred to as O *K* 4th XES), partly overlaps with the first-order P *L*_{2,3} XES and P *L*₃ XES emission, leading to an emission feature seemingly at 132.5 eV (in reality, it is produced by photons with energy 4 × the scale value). Since this feature belongs to a higher-order photon emission from oxygen, it can be observed in the P *L*_{2,3} RIXS maps even at excitation energies that are lower than the P *L*_{2,3}-excitation, see **Figure S4**.

Confirming that the emission feature at 132.5 eV arises from O *K* 4th XES, the O *K* XES of two oxygen-containing P-compounds with different oxidation states, namely H₃P⁽³⁺⁾O₃ and H₃P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, were also measured in first diffraction order. These measurements were carried out in the same end-station after the acquisition of P *L*_{2,3} XES and P *L*₃ XES using the high-resolution spectrometer of the beamline ². For these experiments, the excitation energy was set to 580 eV by using the medium energy grating of the monochromator with an entrance and exit slit of 50 μm. For the calibration of emission energy, O *K* RIXS were recorded with the same configurations as the O *K* XES, and the emission energy was calibrated using the elastic peak of the RIXS maps. Following successful O *K* XES acquisition, the recorded O *K* emission energy was divided by a factor of 4, and the O *K* XES is plotted together with the P *L*_{2,3} XES and P *L*₃ XES. As illustrated in **Figure S3**, the divided O *K* XES matches the feature at 132.5 eV on the P *L*_{2,3} XES energy scale, confirming that it belongs to O *K* 4th XES.

Figure S3. P $L_{2,3}$ XES (black), P L_3 XES (gray), and O K XES (red) of $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(3+)}\text{O}_3$ and $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$. Light red curves illustrate the O K XES spectra after the recorded O K emission energy scale is divided by a factor of 4. O K XES spectra were recorded with the excitation energy of 580 eV. The P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES were normalized to zero at baseline at the background and to one at the feature around 132.5 eV. The O K XES spectra were normalized to zero at the background and to one at spectral maxima.

For an accurate representation of the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra, the O K 4th emission feature is subtracted from the P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra with the following procedure:

- (1) XES spectra containing exclusively an O K 4th emission feature were obtained by summing spectra from RIXS maps at excitation energies below the P $L_{2,3}$ -edge as illustrated by the red shaded region in **Figure S4**. Specifically, the lower limit of the excitation energy region was chosen such that only a small contribution from elastic scattering is present in the summation XES spectrum.
- (2) Cosmic ray contributions were subtracted from the summation XES spectrum using the procedure detailed in Section S2.1.
- (3) The summation spectrum was smoothed using a Savitzky-Golay filter with a window size of 7 points. Note that each XES spectrum was recorded with an energy step of 0.017-0.022 eV. Hereafter, it will be referred to as “bare O K 4th XES”.
- (4) The bare O K 4th XES was subtracted from the P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectrum using the following procedure: (a) Both bare O K 4th XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectra were normalized to zero at the baseline and at unity at maximum at 132.5 eV in the O K 4th spectrum. (b) A factor f was multiplied to the bare O K 4th XES and the result was subtracted from the P $L_{2,3}$ XES. Here, the

factor f has a value of: $0 < f \leq 1$, and a maximum possible f was used, such that there is no negative intensity in the subtracted P $L_{2,3}$ XES.

(5) A similar subtraction procedure was conducted for the P L_3 XES spectrum.

The graphical representation of the O $K 4^{\text{th}}$ emission subtraction process for all of the oxygen-containing samples is illustrated in **Figure S4**. It is important to note that this procedure has some limitations. First, a small fraction of the “true” P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES are removed. Additionally, the presence of an elastic scattering peak, corresponding to the intense diagonal features at the bottom of RIXS maps where $E_{\text{excitation}} = E_{\text{emission}}$, can lead to increased intensity at emission energies above 132.5 eV, i.e., after the O $K 4^{\text{th}}$ feature, such as for $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{P}_2^{(4+)}\text{O}_6$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$. Nevertheless, this subtraction is necessary for an accurate representation of P $L_{2,3}$ XES and P L_3 XES spectra, and with this method, the main feature of P $L_{2,3}$ -emission discussed in the main text (i.e., between 115 eV to 132 eV) remains unaltered. A similar routine was similarly used in earlier studies ^{5,6}.

Figure S4. Illustration of O K 4th XES subtraction procedure from the P L_{2,3} XES and P L₃ XES spectra of: (A) H₃P⁽³⁺⁾O₃, (B) Na₂H₂P₂⁽⁴⁺⁾O₆, (C) H₃P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, (D) KH₂P⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, (E) Na₂HP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄, and (F) InP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄. O K 4th XES is determined by integrating XES spectra recorded at the excitation energies marked in the shaded region of RIXS maps (i.e., region below P L_{2,3}-edge excitation), followed by subsequent cosmic rays subtraction and smoothing. Maximum possible O K 4th XES were then subtracted from P L_{2,3} XES and P L₃ XES spectra. Note that P L_{2,3} XES and P L₃ XES spectra are not taken from RIXS maps, but rather the spectra were recorded with significantly higher integration time than the RIXS maps, as detailed in section S1.2.

2.3. Evaluation of the electronic band gap

For the approximation of the electronic band gaps, the valence band maximum (VB_{\max}) and the conduction band minimum (CB_{\min}) were approximated from the P L_3 XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS, respectively. Subsequently, the electronic band gap (E_{gap}) is determined via:

$$E_{\text{gap}} = CB_{\min} - VB_{\max} \quad (\text{S1})$$

In this investigation, two methods were used and compared to approximate the CB_{\min} and the VB_{\max} : the extrapolation method and the inflection point method. With the extrapolation method, the following procedure was used:

- (1) Linear fits were applied to the leading emission feature at high energies in the P L_3 XES spectrum and to the leading absorption feature at low energies in the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS (see red dashed lines in **Figure S5**).
- (2) The VB_{\max} and the CB_{\min} were determined by linearly extrapolating the leading edges of the XES and XAS spectra, respectively, to their intersections with the linear fit of the baseline.
- (3) The E_{gap} was determined by Eq. S1.

Figure S5 illustrates the procedure for the band gap estimation for each P-containing compound. It is important to note that some compounds, such as phosphates, might display strong core excitonic effects which could influence the onset of the leading edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra. In such cases, the band gap obtained with the extrapolation procedure illustrated above will be smaller than the ground-state band gap of the compound. In fact, for the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS of $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ and $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, a weak pre-peak-like feature was observed (feature marked with * in **Figure S5**), and currently, it is unclear whether the feature arises due to core excitonic effects or due to electronic transition to unoccupied states above the band gap. Therefore, to take into account the possible influence of core excitonic states and to better gauge the uncertainty of the approximated band gap, the CB_{\min} was approximated by the average between the CB_{\min} determined using linear extrapolation conducted at both: the pre-peak-like feature and (ii) the main rising edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS.

Additionally, it is important to note that in this method, VB_{\max} is determined through linear extrapolation of the leading edge P L_3 XES spectrum, rather than P $L_{2,3}$ XES data. The choice of using P L_3 XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS to derive the band gap is based on the nature of the electronic transitions involved. Specifically, the first absorption feature (at low photon energies) in the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectrum, which is used to extrapolate the CB_{\min} is assumed to mainly occur due to the P L_3 transition, i.e., the electronic transition from the P $2p_{3/2}$ core level to unoccupied states. Thus, to ensure accurate determination of the band gap, the VB_{\max} is derived from the P L_3 XES spectrum, which predominantly corresponds to the transition from occupied states to the created P $2p_{3/2}$ core hole. In contrast, the P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectrum includes contributions from both P L_3 and P L_2 transitions (i.e., transition into $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$ core holes). As such the leading edge (at high photon energies) of the P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectrum is dominated by P L_2

contributions, which – if used for the band gap determination – leads to a band gap value that is overestimated by the $2p_{3/2} - 2p_{1/2}$ doublet separation. Although a spin-orbit splitting correction can be applied to the P $L_{2,3}$ XES data to approximate the P L_3 contribution, accurate determination of the emission edge remains challenging. This is due to (1) the partial overlap between the L_2 and L_3 contributions and (2) the shape of the P L_3 emission edge may differ compared to the P $L_{2,3}$ spectrum for certain compounds; as also observed in related XES studies using RIXS and XES at the S $L_{2,3}$ -edge^{7,8}. Therefore, all band gap determinations in this study were performed exclusively using the experimentally measured P L_3 XES data.

The uncertainty of the electronic band gap is approximated as:

$$\sigma_{\text{band gap}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{CBmin}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{VBmax}}^2} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where σ_{CBmin} and σ_{VBmax} are the uncertainties associated with CB_{min} and VB_{max} , respectively. σ_{VBmax} is mainly governed by the resolution of the XES experiments, and therefore, it is assumed to be the same as the XES resolution (σ_{XES}), see Section S1.3. The σ_{CBmin} is estimated as:

$$\sigma_{\text{CBmin}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{BL. exc. photon}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{nat. width}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{en.step}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{std. dev.}}^2} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $\sigma_{\text{BL. exc. photon}}$ is the resolution of the exciting photon from the beamline (0.13 eV for the setting of the monochromator used in these experiments, see Section S1.3), $\sigma_{\text{nat. width}}$ is the natural width of the P $L_{2,3}$ transition (0.03 eV, as according to Ref.⁴), $\sigma_{\text{en. step}}$ is the energy step of the XAS measurements (0.1 eV), and $\sigma_{\text{std. dev.}}$ is the standard deviation between CB_{min} determined by using the extrapolation method conducted at both: the pre-peak-like feature and (ii) the main rising edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS. If the CB_{min} is only estimated through linear extrapolation on the main rising edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS, the term $\sigma_{\text{std. dev.}}$ is not included in the calculation. The estimated band gap, as well as the respective uncertainties of the band gap, are provided in **Table S3**.

In addition to the extrapolation method previously discussed for estimating the CB_{min} , an alternative approach was employed to approximate CB_{min} using the inflection point of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectrum, as shown in **Figure S6**. This method was explored to assess whether it could provide a more accurate estimate of the CB_{min} , particularly for compounds exhibiting strong core excitonic effects that may influence the onset of the leading edge in the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectrum. Please note that for some compounds, strong 1st derivative maxima were not observed, such as for: $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, $\text{KH}_2\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, and $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ (as shown in **Figure S6.F-I**). Instead, the 1st derivative showed multiple data points with intensities comparable to the global maximum of the 1st derivative intensity. In such cases, the inflection point was determined by first identifying the excitation energies of the data points with comparable intensity to the global maximum of the 1st derivative, and then calculating their average. The band gap was subsequently calculated using Eq. S1 and the uncertainty was estimated using Eq. S3. It is important to note that the $\sigma_{\text{std. dev.}}$ term in Eq. S3 was only applied to compounds where a strong 1st derivative

maximum was not observed. In these cases, the standard deviation was calculated based on the variation among data points with intensities comparable to the global maximum of 1st derivative of absorption.

To validate the accuracy of the different methods used to approximate band gaps, we compared our results with reference values available in the literatures⁹⁻¹⁷, see **Figure S7** and **Table S3**. For phosphides and red-P⁽⁰⁾ compounds, both the extrapolation and inflection point methods show good agreement with reference values. However, for certain oxygen-containing P-compounds, the extrapolation method seems to demonstrate better agreement with the referenced literature. This discrepancy arises because the first absorption maxima in some P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra likely result from the convolution of multiple transitions, as prominently observed for Na₂HP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄ and InP⁽⁵⁺⁾O₄ (see panels H and I, **Figure S6**). In such cases, the CB_{\min} determined using the inflection point method is inaccurate. Therefore, the extrapolation method is preferred in this study, as it provides a more reliable representation of the band gap. For this reason, the band gaps discussed in the main text are derived solely using the extrapolation method.

Figure S5. Illustration of the extrapolation procedure to estimate the electronic band gap from the the linear fit of the last emission feature of the P L_3 XES spectra to the baseline and of the first absorption feature of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra to the baseline: (A) GaP $^{(3-)}$, (B) InP $^{(3-)}$, (C) red-P $^{(0)}$, (D), H $_3$ P $^{(3+)}O_3$, (E) Na $_2$ H $_2$ P $_2^{(4+)}O_6$, (F) H $_3$ P $^{(5+)}O_4$, (G) KH $_2$ P $^{(5+)}O_4$, (F), Na $_2$ HP $^{(5+)}O_4$, and (I) InP $^{(5+)}O_4$. Note that for H $_3$ P $^{(3+)}O_3$ and Na $_2$ HP $^{(5+)}O_4$ (panels D and H), the weak feature *o* was excluded from the linear extrapolation, as it might be ascribed to an imperfect subtraction of the O K 4th XES. For Na $_2$ HP $^{(5+)}O_4$ and InP $^{(5+)}O_4$ (panels H and I), the weak pre-edge feature * arises either due to excitonic effects or to electronic transition to unoccupied states above the band gap.

Figure S6. Illustration of inflection point determination (red dashed lines) from the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS of: (A) $\text{GaP}^{(3-)}$, (B) $\text{InP}^{(3-)}$, (C) $\text{red-P}^{(0)}$, (D), $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(3+)}\text{O}_3$, (E) $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{P}_2^{(4+)}\text{O}_6$, (F) $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, (G) $\text{KH}_2\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, (F), $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, and (I) $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$. Please note that for several compounds, such as $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, $\text{KH}_2\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, and $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ (panels F-I), strong 1st absorption maxima were not observed, presumably since the 1st absorption maxima result from the convolution of several transitions. In this case, the inflection point was derived by first determining the data points whose intensity is comparable with the 1st derivation maxima (golden dashed lines and red dashed lines in panels F-I), then the inflection point is defined by the average between those points. As such, for these compounds, the inflection point-approximated CB_{\min} , is much less accurate compared to the other compounds (such as: InP, GaP, or red-P).

Figure S7. Comparison of the estimated electronic band gap estimated from the experimental data presented in this work and references available in the literature⁹⁻¹⁸. Detailed values of the experimentally derived band gap, the respective uncertainties, as well as the reported values from published literature, are provided in **Table S3**.

Table S3. Valence band maximum (VB_{\max}), conduction band minimum (CB_{\min}) resulting band gap, and respective uncertainty of the investigated P-containing compounds derived from P L_3 XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra. The CB_{\min} estimation from the inflection point of P $L_{2,3}$ XAS is reproduced from Ref. ¹ Comparisons with the band gap values available in the literature ⁹⁻¹⁷ and the methods used to derive the respective band gaps are also reported: \emptyset optical spectroscopy: UV-Vis (absorption or diffuse reflectance mode) or photoluminescence spectroscopy; \dagger combination of XES and XAS data (specifically by using both: (i) P L_3 XES and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS, and (ii) O K XES and O K XAS); \ddagger combination of ultraviolet photoemission spectroscopy (UPS) and electron energy loss spectroscopy experiments (EELS). *For the $\text{Na}_2\text{HP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ and $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$, given that a small pre-peak-like feature was observed and the origin of the said feature is currently still unclear, extrapolation method was conducted by linear fit and subsequent extrapolation to baseline at (i) pre-peak-like feature and (ii) rising main edge of P $L_{2,3}$ XAS, as previously discussed and illustrated in **Figure S5**. **For these compounds, strong 1st derivative maxima were not observed, rather the 1st derivative showed multiple data points with intensities comparable to the global maximum of the 1st derivative intensity. Hence, the inflection point was determined by first identifying the excitation energies of the data points with comparable intensity to the global maximum of the 1st derivative, and then calculating their average, as previously discussed and illustrated in **Figure S6**.

Samples	VB_{\max} (eV)	CB_{\min} (eV)		Band gap \pm uncertainty (eV)		Literature band gap (eV) (respective reference)
		Extrapolation	Inflection point	Extrapolation	Inflection point	
GaP ⁽³⁻⁾	128.4	130.7	130.94	2.3 ± 0.2	2.54 ± 0.2	2.25 \emptyset^9
InP ⁽³⁻⁾	129.12	130.38	130.44	1.26 ± 0.2	1.32 ± 0.2	1.27 \emptyset^{10} ; 1.34 \emptyset^{11}
Red-P ⁽⁰⁾	129.52	130.91	131.14	1.39 ± 0.2	1.62 ± 0.2	1.4 – 2.0 \emptyset^{18} ; 1.8 \emptyset^{12}
H₃P ^{(3+)O₃}	132.26	136.27	137.32	4.01 ± 0.2	5.06 ± 0.2	-
Na₂H₂P₂ ^{(4+)O₆}	130.58	136.33	136.84	5.75 ± 0.2	6.26 ± 0.2	-
H₃P ^{(5+)O₄}	130.65	137.3	137.251**	6.65 ± 0.2	6.96**; 7.78**	-
			138.07**		7.01 \pm 0.6 (average)	
KH₂P ^{(5+)O₄}	130.29	136.85	137.80**	6.56 ± 0.2	8.68**; 7.51**	6.4 \dagger^{13} ; 7.1 \emptyset^{14} ; 7.2 \emptyset^{15} ; 8.4 \emptyset^{16}
			138.97**		8.10 \pm 0.8 (average)	
Na₂HP ^{(5+)O₄}	132.56	136.21* (pre-edge) ; 137.24* (main-edge)	138.82**	3.65* (pre-edge); 4.68* (main-edge)	5.79**; 6.26**	-
			138.35**		4.17 \pm 0.8 (average)	
InP ^{(5+)O₄}	130.04	134.49* (pre-edge); 135.41* (main edge)	137.9**	4.45* (main-edge); 5.37* (main-edge)	7.86**; 8.18**	4.5 \ddagger^{15}
			138.55**		4.91 \pm 0.7 (average)	

2.4. Alignment of *ab initio* calculated pDOS with XAS and XES spectra

To align the *ab initio* calculated pDOS, the XAS and XES spectra were plotted relative to the Fermi level (E_F). Given that E_F lies between VB_{\max} and CB_{\min} , and E_F cannot be directly estimated from XAS and XES data, it is assumed for simplicity that the E_F lies in the middle of the electronic band gap, i.e., $E_F = VB_{\max} + (E_{\text{gap}}/2)$, see gold dashed lines in **Figure S8**.

Figure S8. P $L_{2,3}$ XES, P L_3 XES, and P $L_{2,3}$ XAS plotted against both (i) photon energy and (ii) relative to the Fermi level for P-containing compounds with: (A) no ligand: red-P⁽⁰⁾, (B) a metallic ligand: InP⁽³⁻⁾, (C) metallic and oxygen ligand: InP^{(5+)O₄}. Gold dashed lines between the XES and XAS spectra represent the estimated Fermi energy (E_F). The spectra are normalized to zero at the baseline and to 1 at the strongest peak of the P L_3 XES and at the main edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra. For InP^{(5+)O₄} (panel C), the CB_{\min} was estimated as an average between the extrapolation from the pre-peak (dashed green line) and (ii) the main edge of the P $L_{2,3}$ XAS (dashed red line), as discussed in Section S2.3.

3. Direct P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectra comparison between several oxygen-containing P-compounds

Figure S9 illustrates an example of a direct comparison between several oxygen-containing P-compounds with different ligands.

Figure S9. Exemplary direct P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectra comparison between O-containing P-compounds with different ligands. Example are given between $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ and **(A)** $\text{H}_3\text{P}^{(3+)}\text{O}_3$, **(B)** $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{P}_2^{(4+)}\text{O}_6$, **(C)** $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ (on the top panels). The (bottom panels) illustrate the spectral difference between the P $L_{2,3}$ XES data shown in the top panels.

As illustrated in **Figure S9**, albeit the difference is subtle, direct P $L_{2,3}$ XES data comparison between different oxygen-containing P-compounds shows that each compound exhibits a unique spectral feature. As such, speciation of a specific P-containing compound can be made by using the P $L_{2,3}$ XES spectral datasets presented in this study, for instance by fingerprinting unique spectral features displayed by a specific P-containing compound (e.g., the dashed lines shown in **Figure S9**), or by linear combination analysis (as shown in Ref. ¹⁹).

4. Density of states projected onto s , p , d -states of each atomic species

Figure S10. Density of states of (A) $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ and (B) $\text{InP}^{(3-)}$ projected onto: (*top panels*): s , p , and d -states for Phosphorus atoms (P pDOS); (*center panels*): s , p , and/or d -states of non-phosphorus atomic species in the compound (e.g., indium and/or oxygen); (*bottom panels*): Overlap between the pDOS of the P p -states and the pDOS projected into each state of different atoms in the compounds.

Figure S10.A. shows a larger overlap between occupied P p -states and occupied O p -states compared to the overlap between P p -states and other oxygen and/or indium-occupied states in $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$. Similarly, the overlap between P p -states and O p -states in the $\text{InP}^{(5+)}\text{O}_4$ is larger than the overlap between P p -states and other indium occupied states in $\text{InP}^{(3-)}$ (see **Figure S10.B**).

5. References

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